

Optimization of the distribution of small scale Linear Fresnel Reflectors on roofs of urban buildings

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Abstract

This paper analyses the optimization of the distribution of small-scale linear Fresnel reflectors on roofs of urban buildings. The effects of the two major design parameters (i.e. the form and orientation of the available roof area) on the performance of the reflectors are assessed. We present three new algorithms, related to the classical packing mathematical problem, to develop the optimization method. As decision variables, we use the mirror length and the mirror field width (bounded between upper and lower bounds), jointly with the spacing arrangement of the reflectors. The specific objective is to maximize the collection area considering gaps and shadows. To this end, we will optimize the arrangement, number and dimensions of the reflectors. Finally, we present examples based on real cases and analyse the convergence and accuracy of the algorithms, as well as the required computational effort.

Keywords:

Small-scale Linear Fresnel Reflector, Urban residential buildings

1. Introduction

By 2014, 54% of the world's population was living in urban areas, collectively consuming 75% of global resources; while by 2050, the figure of urban population is forecast to reach 66% [1]. Urban environments are accordingly considered to be important points for the installation of renewable energy technologies. One of the biggest energy consumers in the European Union (EU) is the building sector, accounting for more than 40% of the final energy

consumption [2]. For this reason, the EU promotes a series of directives to encourage the use of energy from renewable sources in buildings [3]. Furthermore, European standards [4] require new buildings to obtain part of the energy needed for the hot water service from solar sources, depending on the climate zone and the total hot water demand.

There are various renewable energy systems that can be used in the building sector for the production of electricity and heat [5], [6]. Solar thermal and photovoltaic systems are currently the most widely used, especially in regions where the annual solar radiation is high, as is the case in the countries of Southern Europe. In these regions, there is a steadily increasing number of installations in the form of domestic solar hot water systems and grid-connected photovoltaic systems. Furthermore, renewable energy systems for space heating and cooling are being developed. Thus, solar energy technologies are called to provide a viable alternative to fossil energy systems.

Solar thermal systems can basically be classified into two types of solar collectors: non-concentrating collectors and concentrating collectors. A non-concentrating collector has the same area for intercepting and for absorbing sun's beam radiation. In a concentrating collector, the absorbing area is smaller than the intercepting area, thereby increasing the solar radiation. In addition, the operating temperature of both systems is different. The types and characteristics of solar collectors are shown by [7].

There are many studies on the use of Flat plate collector (*FPCs*) in buildings (see, for example [8], [9], [10], or [11]). However, there are not many studies on the use of linear Fresnel reflectors (*LFRs*) in buildings. *LFRs* are used, for example, in [12] and [13], in domestic water heating; in [14], in the heating/cooling of buildings; and in [15], in the absorption air cooled Solar-GAX cycle.

Various *LFR* configurations have been proposed in the literature (see [16]). In the 'conventional' central *LFR*, there are two main blocks: the primary reflector system and the receiver system. The primary reflector system is composed of a frame where rows of mirrors are located. The receiver system consists of one or multiple circular absorber tubes and a receiver cavity, and is located at a certain height from the primary reflector system. In contrast, in the compact linear Fresnel concentrator (*CLFC*) (see [17]), there is a linear absorber at each side of the mirror array so that consecutive mirrors point to different absorbers.

Different configurations of the receiver system have been studied. For example: (i) two linear receivers on separate towers with double row tube

arrangements of branch tubes [17]; (ii) a receiver consisting of a bundle of tubes parallel to the mirror array [18]; and (iii) receivers with other optical designs, including circular-cylindrical and parabolic cylindrical mirrors [19].

A small-scale linear Fresnel reflector (*SSLFR*) has the configuration of a ‘conventional’ central *LFR*. The possibility of longitudinal movement of the *SSLFR* is the main difference with respect to the large-scale *LFR*. In large-scale *LFRs* the study of the device’s longitudinal behaviour is not usually performed for two reasons: the absorber size does not permit any configuration allowing the modification of its position, and the influence of the longitudinal position can be considered irrelevant in percentage terms with respect to the total length of the absorber.

The position of the mirrors and the absorber of an *SSLFR* can be adjusted using three different movements (see Fig. 1), as shown in [20] and [21]. First, the mirrors can be rotated on the north-south axis, so as to follow the sun’s daily movement. Second, the mirror row can be rotated on the east-west axis. Finally, the receiver can also be rotated on the east-west axis. A prototype with these characteristics has been manufactured at a vocational training school (CIFP-Mantenimiento y Servicios a la Producción) in La Felguera, Asturias, Spain. These three movements have to be taken into account, especially if several *SSLFRs* are to be installed on a building roof.

Roofs are optimal locations for *SSLFRs*, as well as for *FPCs*. However, roofs of urban buildings are generally not designed or built to house renewable energy systems. Available roof area has in fact been identified as a major limiting factor in achieving zero energy buildings, especially for taller buildings[22]. The estimation of the roof area has been the subject of many studies, for example: [23], [24], [25], and [26].

In this paper we analyse the optimization of the distribution of *SSLFRs* on the roofs of urban buildings. In the study, the roof orientation and the available roof area are known parameters. The decision variables are the dimensions of the *SSLFRs* (length and width), which are bounded between upper and lower bounds. In addition, minimum distances between *SSLFRs* are considered in order to allow maintenance and to avoid shadowing effects. As a result of the characteristics of this optimization problem, it can be regarded as new type of two-dimensional rectangle packing problem. Although various types of packing problems have been widely studied, to the best of our knowledge, this particular packing problem has not been addressed in the literature so far.

The paper is organized as follows. The statement of the problem is presented in Section 2, describing the parameters of the *SSLFR* and the roof parameters. Section 3 includes a study of the transversal and longitudinal shadows between *SSLFRs*. The optimization of the distribution of *SSLFRs* on roofs is presented in Section 4, including the description of three different packing algorithms. Section 5 shows numerical results obtained using the three packing algorithms described in the previous section. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the main conclusions of this study.

Fig. 1. Schematic of an *SSLFR* with three movements.

Nomenclature

A	Mirror Field Area (m^2)	l_{ciai}	Length of the circumference illuminated on the absorber tube by the i -th mirror (m)
AR	Aspect ratio	l_a	Total illuminated length of the absorber tube (m)
A_T	Total mirror field area (m^2)	l_s	Length step (m)
A_{ar}	Available roof area (m^2)	N	Number of reflectors
$A_{effe\ i}$	Effective area of the absorber tube (m^2)	n	Number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror
A_r	Roof area (m^2)	n_u	Optimal number of reflectors
a	Length of the available roof area (m)	ns_L	Number of discretization sub-intervals used for L
b	Width of the available roof area (m)	ns_W	Number of discretization sub-intervals used for W
C_{BC}	Building components coefficient		
C_{IA}	Inclination angle coefficient		
C_L	Longitudinal component of the reflected radiation		

Nomenclature

C_{RT}	Roof-type coefficient	O_r	Roof orientation ($^\circ$)
C_S	Shadowing coefficient	Q	Total power absorbed (W)
C_{Ti}	Transversal component of the reflected radiation for the i -th mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$)	S_t	Transversal shading of the absorber tube (m)
CL_g	Cleanliness factor of the glass	t	Computing time (sec)
CL_m	Cleanliness factor of the mirror	W	Mirror field width (m)
D	Diameter of the absorber tube (m)	W_M	Mirror width (m)
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance (W/m^2)	W_{ai}	Width illuminated on the absorber by the i -th by mirror (m)
d	Separation between two consecutive mirrors (m)	α_b	Absorptivity of the material of which the absorber tube is made
$eb, e'b$	Terrace boundary distances (m)	α_i	Angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line connecting the center point of each mirror to the focal point ($^\circ$)
e_h	Transversal maintenance distance (m)	α_S	Height angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
e_v	Longitudinal maintenance distance (m)	β_a	Angle between the absorber tube and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
F_r	Roof form	β_i	Tilt of the i -th mirror ($^\circ$)
f	Height of the receiver (m)	β_M	Angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
IAM	Incidence angle modifier	γ_S	Azimuth of the sun ($^\circ$)
L	Reflector length (m)	η_{opt}	Optical efficiency (%)
L_M	Length of the mirrors (m)	θ_{IA}	Inclination angle for residential roofing ($^\circ$)
L_a	Length of the single absorber tube (m)	θ_i	Angle between the normal to the mirror and the angle of incidence of the sun ($^\circ$)
L_i	Position of i -th mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$) (m)	θ_L	Lateral incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_l	Distance between the center of two consecutive reflectors (m)	θ_l	Longitudinal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_t	Distance between the central point of one SSLFR and the starting point of the following SSLFR (m)	θ_t	Transversal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
μ	Angle between the reflected ray and the normal to the NS axis ($^\circ$)	θ_z	Zenith angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
ρ	Reflectivity of the primary mirrors	λ	Latitude angle ($^\circ$)
		τ	Transmissivity of the glass

2. Statement of the problem

In order to estimate the available roof area for the installation of *SSLFRs* (see Fig. 1), several building characteristics have to be taken into account: number, height, construction typologies, orientation, inclination, location, shading, and building components (such as chimneys, elevator machine rooms, fans, and plumbing vents). Due to the complexity of today's urban settings, it is necessary to simplify the different building forms.

To address this problem, [27] analysed two simplified forms: courts and pavilions. A pavilion and a court are shown in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b), respectively, where black is used for building roofs. Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 2(d) present two archetypal urban patterns with several pavilions and courts, respectively. This division was later used by a large number of studies. Courts and pavilions respectively represent traditional and contemporary building forms, and can be found in many countries.

Fig. 2. Simplified urban forms.

Fig. 3. Generic urban forms.

These two forms from [27] have been subsequently reviewed by [28], resulting in six basic forms (see Fig. 3): a) Pavilions, b) Slabs, c) Terraces, d) Terrace-courts, e) Pavilion-courts, and f) Courts. This paper adopts the pavilion urban form, due to its simplicity and because the calculations can be extrapolated to the remaining urban forms.

Roof inclination is a important parameter for determining the roof area. In urban buildings, roof types are broadly grouped into flat roofs and pitched roofs. Pitched roofs include: the shed roof, gable roof, cross gable roof, saltbox roof, hipped or hip roof, cross hipped roof, gambrel roof, and pyramid roof. Fig. 4 summarizes the established pitched roof typology for generic urban forms: (a) Flat Roof, (b) Shed Roof, (c) Gable Roof, (d) Saltbox Roof, (e) Gambrel Roof, (f) Hipped or Hip Roof, and (g) Pyramid Roof.

Fig. 4. Roof types for generic urban forms.

The parameters that influence the installation of *SSLFRs* on building roofs are of two types: those intrinsic to the *SSLFR* and those relating to the roof. The potential number of *SSLFRs* to be installed on a roof strongly depend on these parameters.

2.1. Intrinsic parameters of the *SSLFR*

These parameters determine the transversal and longitudinal behaviour of the *SSLFR* [20], [21]. Considering an *SSLFR* aligned horizontally in a north-south orientation, the angle of incidence of solar radiation will be calculated in two projection planes: the transversal incidence angle (θ_t), and the longitudinal incidence angle (θ_l). The transversal incidence angle (θ_t) is defined as the angle between the vertical and the projection of the sun vector on the east-west plane (the plane orthogonal to the absorber tube); while the longitudinal incidence angle (θ_l) is defined as the angle between the vertical and the projection of the sun vector on the north-south plane. The relative position of the Sun with respect to the *SSLFR* is determined using the well-known Solpos algorithm [29].

The basic parameters used in the transversal study are as follows: n is the number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror (the total number of mirrors of the *SSLFR* is $2n + 1$), W_M is the mirror width, d is the separation between two consecutive mirrors, L_i is the position with respect to the central mirror of the i -th mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$), β_i is the mirror tilt of the i -th

mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$), D is the diameter of the absorber tube, and f is the height of the receiver.

The basic parameters used in the longitudinal study are as follows: β_M is the angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane, β_a is the angle between the absorber tube and the horizontal plane, θ_z is the zenithal solar angle, L_M is the mirror length, and L_a is the total length of the single absorber tube.

Fig. 5. Parameters of an *SSLFR*.

Fig. 5 shows a ground plan of an *SSLFR*. The mirror field width (W) and the mirror field area (A) can be calculated as:

$$W = 2 \cdot L_n + W_M$$

$$A = W \cdot L_M$$

In order to calculate the energy absorbed by the absorber tube, we will use the equation presented in [21], which is particularly suitable for *SSLFRs*:

$$Q = \sum_{i=0}^{2 \cdot n} DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} \cdot IAM_i \cdot A_{effe i}$$

where:

(i) DNI is the direct normal irradiance. In the present study, DNI is discretized every 10 minutes.

(ii) η_{opt} is the total optical yield, which is calculated considering the reflectivity of the mirrors (ρ), the cleanliness factors of the mirrors (CI_m) and

of the glass covering the secondary absorber (CI_g), the transmissivity of this glass (τ), and the absorptivity of the material of which the absorber tube is made (α_b):

$$\eta_{opt} = (\rho \cdot CI_m) \cdot (\tau \cdot CI_g \cdot \alpha_b)$$

Although some of these parameters, especially τ , should change with the angle of incidence (see [30]), in this study they are considered constant for the sake of simplicity (see [31] and [32]). These values are: $\rho = 0.94$ (see [33]), $CI_m = CI_g = 0.96$ (see [34]), if $\alpha_i \leq 20^\circ$, $\tau = 0.87$, if $20^\circ \leq \alpha_i \leq 30^\circ$, $\tau = 0.85$ (see [30]).

(iii) IAM_i considers the variation in the optical performance of an *SSLFR* for varying ray incidence angles, by the i -th mirror, which is calculated using the equation shown by [35]:

$$IAM_i = \left[C_L^2 + C_{Ti}^2 + 2 \cdot C_L \cdot C_{Ti} \cdot \cos \widehat{C_L C_{Ti}} \right]^{1/2}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n$$

where C_L (common to all mirrors) and C_{Ti} (different for each mirror) are the components of the reflected radiation, the values of which are given by:

$$C_L = \cos \gamma_S \cdot \cos \theta_L; \quad C_{Ti} = \frac{\cos \alpha_S \cdot \sin \gamma_S \cdot \cos \theta_i}{\sin \theta_t}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n$$

(iv) $A_{effe i}$ is the effective area of the absorber tube by the i -th mirror that is actually illuminated, which is calculated using the equation shown in [35]:

$$A_{effi} = l_{ciai} \cdot l_a; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n$$

where l_{ciai} is the length of the circumference illuminated on the absorber tube by the i -th mirror, and l_a is the total illuminated length of the absorber tube.

A MATLAB code was compiled to trace the Sun's rays. This code uses geometric optics to calculate ray intersections with the primary reflector system. As an example, Fig. 6 presents ray tracing simulations for an *SSLFR*. For the sake of clarity, this visualization shows a reduced number of rays. This simulation was carried out on June 21st (Summer solstice), solar time 10:30, and geographic location: Almeria (Spain), with latitude $36^\circ 50' 07'' N$, longitude $02^\circ 24' 08'' W$ and altitude $22(m)$.

Fig. 6. Ray tracing simulations for an SSLFR .

2.2. The roof parameters

The roof-related parameters are as follows: roof area (A_r), available roof area (A_{ar}), roof form (F_r), and roof orientation (O_r). These parameters are described below.

(1) The available roof area (A_{ar}) is the area that can be used for installing *SSLFRs*. Several authors have applied Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques to determine the available area on roofs of urban buildings (see [36], [23] and [37]). A_{ar} may also be calculated using the following equation:

$$A_{ar} = A_r \cdot C_{BC} \cdot C_S \cdot C_{RT} \cdot C_{IA}$$

where:

(i) C_{BC} is the building components coefficient, used to take into account components such as chimneys, elevator machine rooms, fans, and plumbing vents. Several studies have concluded that roof-mounted residential building components reduce the available roof area for renewable energy systems to a figure between 21% of the roof [38] and 30% of the roof [25]. Therefore this coefficient can vary between 0.7 and 0.79.

(ii) C_S is the shadowing coefficient, used to correct the shadows caused by other buildings, or by the roof itself. A 3D city model would be necessary to precisely determine this coefficient. It is customary to assume the value found by [23], which is obtained as a function of the representative building typology.

(iii) C_{RT} is the roof-type coefficient [25]. For flat roofs, $C_{RT} = 1$, while for pitched roofs, this coefficient depends on the number of pitches. If *SSLFRs* are to be installed on only one of the two pitches of the roof, $C_{RT} = 0.5$.

(iv) C_{IA} is the inclination angle coefficient due to the slope of the pitch, and can be calculated as:

$$C_{IA} = \cos(\theta_{IA})$$

where θ_{IA} is the inclination angle for residential roofing. As an example, the Spanish Technical Building Code [39] states that the slope of the pitch has to be designed in accordance with the roofing material. For a flat roof, $C_{IA} = 1$.

(2) The form of the roof area (F_r) is defined as the ratio between the length (a) and width (b) of the available roof area:

$$F_r = \frac{a}{b}$$

One of the most important ways of characterizing the installation of an *SSLFR* is via its aspect ratio (AR), defined as:

$$AR = \frac{W}{L_M}$$

The *SSLFR* aspect ratio (AR) is related to F_r , as F_r imposes a limit to the value of AR . The study of this relationship is one of the objectives of this paper.

(3) The roof orientation (O_r) is defined by the angle that forms the north-south direction and the terrace edges. In our study, every *SSLFR* is aligned in the north-south direction and we assume that the terrace edges are parallel to our reference axes ($x - y$). Thus, the roof orientation is given by the angle (α) between the north-south direction and the positive half axis of y .

3. Study of the shadows

This section describes the mathematical method developed to maximize the roof area filled by a set of *SSLFRs*. The objective function to be maximized is the total mirror field area (A_T), given by:

$$A_T = \sum_{i=1}^N W \cdot L$$

where N is the number of reflectors, W is the mirror field width, and L is the reflector length ($L = L_M$). In this study, we assume that all the reflectors are identical in size. The mathematical formulation includes upper and lower bounds for the decision variables W and L , in the following form:

$$W^{\min} \leq W \leq W^{\max}; \quad L^{\min} \leq L \leq L^{\max}$$

The optimization model also considers a transversal maintenance distance (e_h) and a longitudinal maintenance distance (e_v), to be kept between reflectors in order to allow proper inspection, cleaning, and maintenance. Moreover, the model evaluates the frontal and lateral shadows between reflectors.

Fig. 7. Transversal shadows.

Fig 8. Longitudinal shadows.

3.1. Evaluation of the transversal shadow between SSLFRs

As shown in Fig. 7, θ_t is the transversal incidence angle, and L_t is the distance between the central point of one *SSLFR* and the starting point of the following *SSLFR*. Neglecting the effect of the secondary concentrator, L_t is given by:

$$L_t \simeq f \cdot \tan \theta_t$$

The transversal shadow (see Fig. 7) is null provided that the following condition is met:

$$L_t \leq \left(L_n + \frac{W_M}{2} \right)$$

where L_n is the position of the last mirror with respect to the central mirror. When there is a transversal shadow, its value is given by:

$$L_t - \left(L_n + \frac{W_M}{2} \right)$$

The parameters of the *SSLFR* considered here are as follows. Mirror width (W_M): 0.06 (m); vertical distance between the absorber and the mirrors (f): 1.5 (m); mirror thickness: 0.005 (m); mirror length (L_M): 2.0 (m); absorber length (L_a): 2.40 (m); absorber diameter (D): 0.0486 (m); and reflector width (W): 2.076 (m).

The Spanish Technical Building Code [40] states that, in order to minimize shadowing effects, the distance between reflectors has to guarantee a minimum of 4 hours of sunshine around noon on the winter solstice. Applying this standard, on December 21st at 10 : 00 the value of L_t is 1.785 (m), as θ_t is equal to -40.05° . Therefore, there is a transversal shadow of 0.782 (m). For this reason, a transversal maintenance distance (e_h) of 1.0 (m), considered suitable for maintenance purposes, is also sufficient to minimize shadowing effects.

3.2. Evaluation of the longitudinal shadow between *SSLFRs*

Due to lateral symmetry, we need only take into account the central mirror for this study. Defining L_l as the distance between the centre of two consecutive reflectors, the following relations between angles and distances can be verified (see Fig. 8):

$$\begin{aligned} L_l^1 &= \frac{L_M}{2} \cos \beta_M; \quad L_l^2 = \left[f + \frac{L_M}{2} \sin \beta_M + \frac{L_a}{2} \sin \beta_a \right] \tan \theta_z \\ L_l^3 &= \frac{L_M}{2} \sin \beta_M \tan \theta_z; \quad L_l^4 = \frac{L_M}{2} \sin \beta_M \\ L_l &= L_l^1 + L_l^2 + L_l^3 + L_l^4 \end{aligned}$$

When there is lateral shadow (see Fig. 8), its value is given by:

$$L_l^2 + L_l^3$$

Taking into account the Spanish Technical Building Code [40], a longitudinal maintenance distance (e_v) of 1.0 (m), considered suitable for maintenance purposes, is also sufficient to minimize shadowing effects.

4. Optimization of the distribution of *SSLFRs* on roofs

The distribution of *SSLFRs* on roofs of urban buildings is optimized in this paper using three new algorithms that are related to the classical mathematical packing problem. Packing problems are a class of mathematical

optimization problems that attempt to pack objects into containers [41]. The distribution of SSLFRs on roofs is formulated in this paper as a two-dimensional rectangle packing problem.

Imahori et al. review in [42] several types of rectangle packing problems, as follows: (1) Strip packing problem; (2) Area minimization problem; (3) Two-dimensional bin packing problem ([43] and [44]); (4) Two-dimensional knapsack problem ([45] and [46]); (5) Two-dimensional cutting stock problem ([47], [48], [49]); and (6) Pallet loading problem [50]. Table I summarizes the main characteristics of these problems. The notation (f) indicates a fixed parameter, and (v) a variable.

Table I. Characteristics of the packing problems described in [42].

Problem	1	2	3	4	5	6
Items						
number	n	n	n	$set I$	n	$set I$
width	w_i	w_i	w_i	w_i	w_i	w
height	h_i	h_i	h_i	h_i	h_i	h
				$value c_i$	$demand d_i$	
Large object						
number	1	1	N (v)	1	N (v)	1
width	W (f)	W (v)	W (f)	W (f)	W (f)	W (f)
height	H (v)	H (v)	H (f)	H (f)	H (f)	H (f)
Objective	$\min H$	$\min W.H$	$\min N$	$\max value$	$\min N$	$\max items$
Packed	n	n	n	$subset I$	n	$subset I$
					d_i copies	Rotated 90°

In computational complexity theory, NP (nondeterministic polynomial time) is a complexity class used to describe certain types of decision problems. Almost all two-dimensional packing problems are known to be NP-hard, and hence it is impossible to solve them exactly in polynomial time. Therefore, heuristic techniques are used to design practical algorithms for these problems.

In this paper we consider a very special type of two-dimensional rectangle packing problem. We have to pack identical rectangles in a fixed rectangle (like, for example, [51]), taking into account additional constraints:

(i) A minimum space must be left between objects for maintenance purposes and to avoid shadowing effects.

(ii) The orientation of the objects is fixed with respect to the container, and in general they are not orthogonal.

(iii) The dimensions of the objects are not fixed, but they are bounded between upper and lower bounds.

To the best of our knowledge, this packing problem has not been addressed in the literature, therefore we are presenting the first algorithms to solve it.

4.1. Three packing algorithms

In addition to considering the necessary maintenance distances between reflectors, $e_h = e_v = 1.0$ (m), there has to be a minimum distance between the terrace boundary and the reflectors, also for maintenance purposes. These distances are designated eb and $e'b$, and a value of 1 (m) is assumed for both of them. Given a terrace of dimensions $a \times b$, we assume that the terrace edges are parallel to our reference axes ($x - y$). Let α be the angle between the N-S direction and the positive half axis of y .

As already stated, the problem consists in packing reflectors with length L and width W , these dimensions being bounded between upper and lower bounds. In this paper we will present three different packing schemes in order to solve this packing problem.

TYPE (I) N-S ALIGNMENT

This packing scheme consists of placing rows of reflectors parallel to the north-south direction. In this scheme (see Fig. 9), we define a base rectangle R_{11} using two vertices A and B , which are located as close as possible to the bottom-right corner of the terrace. From the coordinates of these two vertices A and B , the coordinates of the other two vertices C and D can be easily calculated:

$$R_{11} : \begin{cases} A(eb, e'b + W \sin \alpha) & \rightarrow & D(x_A + L \sin \alpha, y_A + L \cos \alpha) \\ B(eb + W \cos \alpha, e'b) & \rightarrow & C(x_B + L \sin \alpha, y_B + L \cos \alpha) \end{cases}$$

Fig. 9. Type (I) N-S alignment.

Fig. 10. Type (II) E-W alignment.

Once the base rectangle R_{11} has been defined, the packing pattern of the first row is completed by placing horizontally, from right to left, as many rectangles R_{1i} as possible, keeping the necessary distances between them. Clearly, the y coordinates are the same for all the rectangles in the first row. The increase in the x coordinates between one rectangle and the next is given by:

$$\Delta x = \begin{cases} \frac{e_h}{\cos \alpha} + \frac{W}{\cos \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_v + L & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases} ; \quad \Delta y = 0$$

Thus, the coordinates of the four vertices A , B , C , and D of the rectangles in the first row are given by:

$$R_{1i} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (i-1)\Delta x, y_A) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (i-1)\Delta x, y_B) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

From each rectangle in the first row, new rectangles R_{ji} are added in a direction parallel to the N-S direction, using the following relationships:

$$\delta x = \begin{cases} e_v \sin \alpha + L \sin \alpha & \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ 0 & \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases} ; \quad \delta y = \begin{cases} e_v \cos \alpha + L \cos \alpha & \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_v \sin \alpha + W \sin \alpha & \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

$$R_{ji} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (j-1)\delta x, y_A + (j-1)\delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (j-1)\delta x, y_B + (j-1)\delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; \quad j = 1, \dots, m$$

The packing pattern is completed by placing new rectangles R_{k1} ($k = 0, -1, \dots$) vertically aligned with the base rectangle R_{11} . The coordinates of the four vertices of rectangles R_{k1} are given by:

$$\Delta x = 0; \quad \Delta y = \begin{cases} \frac{e_h}{\sin \alpha} + \frac{W}{\sin \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq 0 \\ e_v + L & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$R_{k1} : \begin{cases} A(x_A, y_A + (1 - k)\Delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B, y_B + (1 - k)\Delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; \quad k = 0, -1, \dots$$

Finally, from each rectangle R_{k1} , new rectangles are added in a direction parallel to the N-S direction.

TYPE (II) E-W ALIGNMENT

This second packing scheme consists in placing rows of reflectors parallel to the east-west direction. In this scheme (see Fig. 10), we define a base rectangle R_{11} using two vertices A and B , which are located as close as possible to the upper-right corner of the terrace. The coordinates of the four vertices A , B , C , and D are given by:

$$R_{11} : \begin{cases} A(eb, e'b + L \cos \alpha) & \rightarrow D(x_A + W \cos \alpha, y_A + W \sin \alpha) \\ B(eb + L \sin \alpha, e'b) & \rightarrow C(x_B + W \cos \alpha, y_B + W \sin \alpha) \end{cases}$$

First, the packing pattern of the first column is completed by placing vertically, from top to bottom, as many rectangles R_{1i} as possible. The increase of the y coordinates between one rectangle and the next is given by:

$$\Delta x = 0; \quad \Delta y = \begin{cases} \frac{e_v}{\cos \alpha} + \frac{L}{\cos \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_h + W & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

Thus, the coordinates of the four vertices A , B , C , and D of the rectangles in the first column are given by:

$$R_{i1} : \begin{cases} A(x_A, y_A + (i - 1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B, y_B + (i - 1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; \quad i = 1, \dots, n$$

From each rectangle in the first column, new rectangles R_{ij} are added in a direction perpendicular to the N-S direction, using the following relationships:

$$\delta x = \begin{cases} e_h \cos \alpha + W \cos \alpha & \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_h \sin \alpha + L \sin \alpha & \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases} ; \quad \delta y = \begin{cases} e_h \sin \alpha + W \sin \alpha & \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ 0 & \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

$$R_{ij} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (j-1)\delta x, y_A + (j-1)\delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (j-1)\delta x, y_B + (j-1)\delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; j = 1, \dots, m$$

The packing pattern is completed by placing new rectangles R_{k1} ($k = 0, -1, \dots$) horizontally aligned with the base rectangle R_{11} . The coordinates of the four vertices of rectangles R_{k1} are given by:

$$\Delta x = \begin{cases} \frac{e_v}{\sin \alpha} + \frac{L}{\sin \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq 0 \\ e_h + W & \text{if } \alpha = 0 \end{cases} ; \Delta y = 0$$

$$R_{k1} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (1-k)\Delta x, y_A) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (1-k)\Delta x, y_B) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; k = 0, -1, \dots$$

TYPE (III) X-Y ALIGNMENT

Finally, we present a third packing scheme, inspired by the classic method that inscribes irregular shapes into rectangles. This scheme consists in placing rows of reflectors parallel to the terrace edges and hence parallel to our reference axes ($x-y$). We once again define a base rectangle R_{11} close to the bottom-right corner of the terrace:

$$R_{11} : \begin{cases} A(eb, e'b + W \sin \alpha) & \rightarrow D(x_A + L \sin \alpha, y_A + L \cos \alpha) \\ B(eb + W \cos \alpha, e'b) & \rightarrow C(x_B + L \sin \alpha, y_B + L \cos \alpha) \end{cases}$$

Depending on the parameters of the problem, the distance between reflectors on the x -axis can be given by e_h (case III-A) or by e_v (case III-B), and the distance between reflectors on the y -axis can be given by e_v (case III-A) or by e_h (case III-B). These two cases, III-A and III-B, are shown in Figs. 11 and 12, respectively.

(III-A) In case III-A, the coordinates of the vertices of the rectangles are calculated as follows.

$$R_{1i} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (i-1)\Delta x, y_A) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (i-1)\Delta x, y_B) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; i = 1, \dots$$

$$\Delta x = \begin{cases} \frac{e_h}{\cos \alpha} + \frac{W}{\cos \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_v + L & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases} ; \Delta y = 0$$

$$R_{i1} : \begin{cases} A(x_A, y_A + (i-1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B, y_B + (i-1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; i = 1, \dots$$

$$\Delta x = 0; \quad \Delta y = \begin{cases} \frac{e_v}{\cos \alpha} + \frac{L}{\cos \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_h + W & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

Fig. 11. Type (III-A) X-Y alignment. Fig. 12. Type (III-B) X-Y alignment.

(III-B) In case III-B, the coordinates of the vertices of the rectangles are calculated as follows.

$$R_{1i} : \begin{cases} A(x_A + (i-1)\Delta x, y_A) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B + (i-1)\Delta x, y_B) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; i = 1, \dots$$

$$\Delta x = \begin{cases} \frac{e_v}{\sin \alpha} + \frac{L}{\sin \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_h + W & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases} ; \quad \Delta y = 0$$

$$R_{i1} : \begin{cases} A(x_A, y_A + (i-1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow D \\ B(x_B, y_B + (i-1)\Delta y) & \rightarrow C \end{cases} ; i = 1, \dots$$

$$\Delta x = 0; \quad \Delta y = \begin{cases} \frac{e_h}{\sin \alpha} + \frac{W}{\sin \alpha} & \text{if } \alpha \neq \pi/2 \\ e_v + L & \text{if } \alpha = \pi/2 \end{cases}$$

5. Numerical Examples

This section shows the results obtained with the three types of packing described in the previous section. The optimization algorithm was implemented using the commercial software MathematicaTM.

Table II. Optimal values of r for the three types of packing.

$a \times b$		0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°
10×10	I	0.288	0.210	0.224	0.207	0.224	0.210	0.288
	II	0.288	0.225	0.176	0.210	0.176	0.225	0.288
	III	0.288	0.225	0.201	0.207	0.201	0.225	0.288
20×10	I	0.315	0.245	0.267	0.245	0.243	0.246	0.302
	II	0.315	0.224	0.241	0.247	0.234	0.262	0.302
	III	0.315	0.262	0.225	0.207	0.241	0.281	0.302
10×20	I	0.302	0.246	0.243	0.245	0.267	0.245	0.315
	II	0.302	0.262	0.234	0.247	0.241	0.224	0.315
	III	0.302	0.281	0.241	0.207	0.225	0.262	0.315
30×10	I	0.336	0.262	0.284	0.275	0.262	0.257	0.320
	II	0.336	0.230	0.237	0.264	0.249	0.276	0.320
	III	0.336	0.275	0.233	0.230	0.235	0.288	0.320
10×30	I	0.320	0.257	0.262	0.275	0.284	0.262	0.336
	II	0.320	0.276	0.249	0.264	0.237	0.230	0.336
	III	0.320	0.288	0.235	0.230	0.233	0.275	0.336

As stated in Section 1 (Introduction), a prototype with these characteristics has been manufactured at a vocational training school (CIFP-Mantenimiento y Servicios a la Producción) in La Felguera, Asturias, Spain. The values considered for the upper and lower bounds of the reflector dimensions (width and length) are based on the actual dimensions of the prototype: $W^{\min} = 1.0$ (m); $W^{\max} = 1.5$ (m); $L^{\min} = 2.0$ (m); $L^{\max} = 2.5$ (m). Other authors have used similar dimensions [52].

We consider, without loss of generality, that $e_h = e_v = 1.0$ (m), and $eb = e'b = 1.0$ (m). With regard to the dimensions of the terrace (a and b), we analyse a square case ($F_r = 1$), and also two rectangular cases ($F_r = 2$, and $F_r = 3$). In addition, the influence of the orientation of the terrace is taken into account, varying the angle that the terrace forms with the north-south direction between 0 and 90° .

The algorithm finds, for each packing scheme, the reflector dimensions (width and length) which maximize the total mirror field area. The optimization procedure is in fact a brute force algorithm that evaluates all the possible combinations of width and length between their upper and lower bounds, using a length step, l_s , of 0.1 (m). Nevertheless, the algorithm run-

ning time is about 1 sec on a personal computer (Intel Core 2/2.66 GHz).

The optimal solutions, for each packing scheme (I, II, and III), are shown in Table II. The packing scheme that gives the best result is highlighted using bold typeface. The value shown in this table is the ratio r of the total mirror field area to the total area of the terrace:

$$r = \frac{A_T}{a \cdot b}$$

According to these results, the packaging scheme that gives the best solution depends on the angle of orientation of the terrace. Obviously, when the angle is 0° or 90° , the three packing schemes give the same optimal solution. When the angle is less than 15° or greater than 75° , the best packing scheme is Type III. However, when the angle is between 30° and 60° , the best packing scheme is Type I or Type II.

Fig. 13. Optimal Solution.

As an example, Fig. 13 shows the optimal configurations for a terrace of dimensions $a \times b = 20 \times 10$ (m), with an angle of orientation of 15° (III mode), 45° (II mode), and 60° (I mode). Each configuration shows in the upper part the optimal values of the parameters; namely, from top to bottom: length (L), width (W), r , and number of reflectors (n_u).

Table III shows the energy absorbed by the absorber tube per year, for the optimal configurations depicted in Fig. 13. All the calculations are based on

a sub-hourly distribution of direct normal irradiance in a specific geographic location: Almeria (Spain), with latitude $36^{\circ}50'07''N$, longitude $02^{\circ}24'08''W$, and altitude 22 (m). Derived database and system integrating data [53] have been used to estimate the solar irradiance. Numerical simulations were performed using a MATLAB code [35] which incorporates subroutines, discretized every 10 minutes, to calculate: DNI , mirror position, IAM , l_{ciai} , and l_a . The effects of shading, blocking, and end loss have also been taken into account.

Table III. Energy absorbed by the absorber tube per year (MWh).

Orientation	Mode		
	I	II	III
15°	60.85	71.94	77.08
45°	60.50	67.83	46.59
60°	73.38	66.18	61.66

5.1. Time efficiency and convergence

Although the algorithms presented in this paper were developed for this specific application (the installation of SSLFRs on building roofs), we believe that they could also be useful in problems with similar characteristics. In an application where the number of units to be installed is very high, the computation time of the algorithms is a factor that has to be taken into account.

Table IV and Fig. 14 show the computation time (t) in seconds as a function of the optimal number of reflectors (n_u) for terraces of different sizes. This analysis has been carried out using the following values: $\alpha = 30^{\circ}$, $l_s = 0.1(m)$, $F_r = 3$. The results shown correspond to Type (III) algorithm, yet the other algorithms give similar figures. As can be seen in Fig. 14, the computation time grows linearly with the optimal number of reflectors: $O(n_u)$. Since no potential or exponential growth is obtained, the algorithms could also be used for large-scale problems.

Table IV. Computation time for terraces of different sizes.

$(a \times b)$	n_u	t
(30×10)	20	0.592
$\sqrt{10} (30 \times 10)$	256	4.508
$10 (30 \times 10)$	2472	38.845
$20 (30 \times 10)$	10143	154.379

Fig. 14. Computation time as a function of n_u .

In addition to the size of the terrace, another factor that determines the computation time is the discretization size or length step (l_s) used to evaluate all the possible combinations of width (W) and length (L) between their upper and lower bounds. Table V and Fig. 15 show the computation time (t) in seconds as a function of the number of discretization subintervals considered for W (ns_W) and L (ns_L). This analysis was carried out using the following values: $\alpha = 60^\circ$, $a \times b = 30 \times 10(m)$, $W^{\min} = 1(m)$, $W^{\max} = 1.5(m)$, $L^{\min} = 2(m)$, $L^{\max} = 2.5(m)$. With the lower and upper bounds considered here, $ns_W = ns_L$, though, obviously, these values could be different. As in the previous case, the results shown correspond to the Type (III) algorithm, and the other algorithms also give similar figures. As can be seen in Fig. 15, the computation time also grows linearly with the product of discretization subintervals: $O(ns_W \cdot ns_L)$.

Table V shows also the optimal values of length (L^*), width (W^*), and ratio (r^*) as a function of the length step. By decreasing the length step, the solution quickly converges to its optimal value. The optimal number of reflectors is 24, regardless of the length step value.

Table V. Computation time and optimal solution for different length steps.

l_s	ns_W	ns_L	$ns_W \cdot ns_L$	t	$L^* \times W^*$	r^*
0.1	5	5	25	0.514	2.1×1.4	0.2352
0.05	10	10	100	1.639	2.1×1.45	0.2436
0.01	50	50	2500	33.556	2.14×1.45	0.24824
0.005	100	100	10000	132.601	2.14×1.455	0.249096

Fig. 15. Computation time as a function of $ns_W \cdot ns_L$.

Fig. 16. Value of r as a function of L and W for each l_s .

Fig. 16 shows the value of r as a function of L and W for each of the length step values considered. This figure was produced using Mathematica® via a polynomial interpolation of the values obtained with the algorithm. Obviously, the accuracy depends on the value of the length step. As the length step decreases, the graph approaches a step function.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a mathematical method to optimize the installation of small scale Linear Fresnel Reflectors in urban residential buildings. The influence of the form and orientation of the available roof area is analysed in order to determine the optimal number and arrangement of the reflectors. Shadowing effects are also taken into account. The optimization procedure considers three new packing algorithms, developed specifically for this problem. The results show that the algorithm which provides the best solution depends on the characteristics of each particular problem, i.e. the dimensions and orientation of the terrace, and the values considered for the upper and lower bounds of the reflector dimensions (width and length).

The obtained algorithms could also be useful in other applications with similar characteristics. It has been shown that they could be applied to large-scale problems with very reasonable computing times, given that the computing time grows linearly with the optimal number of reflectors and with the discretization size. The precision of the algorithms depends on the discretization size. The algorithms presented in this paper converge quickly to the optimal solution and are hence a viable alternative bearing in mind that the optimal solution cannot be obtained using conventional methods of differential calculus.

The presented algorithms can be generalized to the study of terraces of irregular form (as a composition of several rectangles). Other possible refinements of the optimization method could be the analysis of some components that are usually found on building roofs: elevator machine rooms, fans, et cetera.

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